

SiC Fiber Reinforced
Glass Ceramic Matrix Composites

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The use of Nicalon type SiC fibers to reinforce lithium aluminosilicate (LAS) and glass ceramic matrix composites has resulted in materials with high tensile strength and toughness. The mechanical properties of this system will be described with emphasis on tensile and flexural strength. The general features of composite stress-strain behavior will be described and it will be shown that composite strength is a function of matrix type, fiber strength, test temperature and test specimen geometry.

The use of glass ceramic matrices will also be shown to be a powerful technique to achieve composites through a wide variety of fabrication approaches. Unidirectionally reinforced plies, woven cloth and chopped fibers can all be used in procedures similar to those current for polymer matrix composites. This permits the fabrication of a wide variety of shapes and sizes of articles and it is anticipated can lead to a particularly economical approach to achieving high performance ceramic composites.

